

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

FROM NATURAL INTELLIGENCE TO ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE USING NEURAL NETWORKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10227601>

Abstract

Computer technologies and programming are widely used in various fields of human activity such as computer science, science and technology, economics, education, mobile communications, transport, space exploration and military science. Moreover, these technologies are developing intensively and at high speed. Today we are talking about artificial intelligence, neural networks, and virtual reality using modern multimedia achievements. This article analyzes the basic concepts of artificial intelligence that arose on the basis of natural intelligence through a neural network - as a natural way of transforming information, as well as the development path and role of these technologies in the scope of human activity.

Keywords: neural networks, artificial intelligence, programming, neurons, virtual reality.

Introduction

Before moving on to such a concept as a neural network, I would like to start with a science called bionics - a science created on the basis of natural processes in living organisms with the aim of applying this knowledge about nature in everyday human reality. Living systems of nature are an example of the lightness and reliability of the structures of buildings, towers, and bridges. Bionics has made significant contributions to aviation, medicine, and even the defense industry. This is a direction in biology and cybernetics, which studies the structural features and vital functions of organisms in order to create new devices, mechanisms, systems and improve existing ones. The great Leonardo da Vinci is called the father of the science of bionics. In the records of this genius, one can find the first attempts at the technical implementation of natural mechanisms. Da Vinci's drawings illustrate his desire to create an aircraft capable of moving its wings, like a flying bird. Note that man-made products of this sci-

ence have much greater capabilities and technical indicators compared to living analogues (e.g., flight speed and altitude, etc.) [6].

Let's move on to the concept of a neural network, which is an artificial intelligence technique that teaches computers to process data similarly to the human brain (see Figure 1). The architecture of neural networks is modeled after the human brain, with artificial neurons interacting to solve problems in a layered structure [4]. Artificial neurons are software modules called nodes, and neural networks are programs or algorithms that use mathematical calculations to perform machine learning processes. This deep learning process allows computers to learn from their mistakes and constantly improve, making intelligent decisions with limited human input. Neural networks can study and model complex relationships between inputs and outputs, such as understanding unstructured data and making general observations without specialized training. For example, they can recognize that two different sentences have the same meaning.

*Fig.1. Neural networks of the human brain
A neural network is a processing method used in artificial intelligence*

A neural network is a method of processing information in which a computer program emulates the functions of the human brain. This is achieved through the use of computing elements that transmit signals to one another, similar to the way neurons in the brain communicate. The concept of neural networks was first proposed by Warren McCullough and Walter Pitts, researchers at the University of Chicago, in 1944. The first neural network that was capable of learning was developed by Frank Rosenblatt, a psychologist at Cornell University, in 1957, although it was only a single-layer network. In the 1980s, as more powerful computers became available, researchers were able to develop neural networks with two and three layers of learning. However, it wasn't until recently, thanks to the computer game industry, that there has been a revival of in-

terest in neural networks and a revolution in deep learning. Modern games require complex calculations to process a large number of operations, which led to the development of graphics processing units (GPUs). GPUs combine thousands of simple processing cores onto a single chip, and their architecture is similar to that of a neural network. This has made it possible to develop "deep learning" by increasing the number of layers in neural networks. As a result, self-learning neural networks have emerged that can process incoming information without the need for special settings. Each neural network is composed of artificial neurons that mimic the functioning of the human brain. These are software modules or nodes that interact and exchange information to solve a problem [2]. A basic neural network contains three layers of artificial neurons (see Figure 2).

Fig.2. Neural network architecture

The following parameters are indicated in this figure:

- input - processes information from the outside, analyzes or classifies it, and transmits it to the next layer;
- hidden (there may be several of them) - analyzes the output data of the previous layer, processes it, and transfers it to the next layer (it is not shown in the picture);
- exit - produces the final result after processing all the data.

Deep neural networks are distinguished by the fact that their artificial neurons in them are connected to each other, and each such connection is assigned a certain weight that reflects its significance. In addition, communication between neurons can be "feedforward." This means that data only flows through them in one direction. This occurs if the value of the "weight" of the connection is lower than the specified one.

When training a neural network, all its "weights" are initially set to random values. The training data are fed to the bottom, or input, layer. They then pass through subsequent layers until they reach the output. During training, the "weights" and thresholds are continually adjusted until the training data consistently produce the same results.

These "weights" help determine the importance of a particular variable in the input data. As each layer passes through, the input data are multiplied by its "weights" and then summed. If the resulting value is above a given threshold, then the neuron is activated and transmits the data to the next level. Depending on

the architecture, neural networks are divided into the following types:

- direct distribution - processes input data and immediately produces the result. Most often used for image and text recognition and data classification;
- recurrent - redirect information back and forth through the layers until the final result is obtained. This type is usually used for forecasting;
- convolutional - process each feature in a separate layer. This type is used in image classification and language processing.

In addition to the main types, there are dozens of subtypes of neural networks. For example, modular networks are essentially a collection of neural networks that work independently of each other to speed up calculations. All tasks that can be solved by a person or a computer can be divided into two categories: routine and non-routine. Routine tasks include those in which it is quite easy to find a universal solution, for example, adding numbers or measuring air temperature.

Artificial intelligence is now commonly called everything that is capable of solving non-routine problems at a level close to humans, and sometimes even better. Such tasks surround us everywhere. Cameras above the road calculate the speed of the car, recognize its sign and issue a fine, and security systems in the subway and airports find criminals in the crowd. All this is today considered as artificial intelligence, although in reality the algorithms underlying each such technology are unique. Only a small number of individuals employ machine learning techniques.

Artificial intelligence is not the name of a single algorithm, but rather a group of methods that are used to solve various kinds of problems. Algorithms that use learning approaches are only a subgroup of the entire set of algorithms commonly called artificial intelligence. Machine learning is an approach in which an algorithm “learns” how to solve a problem. One of the simplest examples of an algorithm using machine learning is, for example, classifying photographs into those with cats and those with dogs.

Fig. 3. Virtual reality in education

Training using virtual reality technologies is a completely new aspect of the educational process. Studying with glasses makes it possible to completely immerse yourself in the learning process and not be distracted by external factors. Learning in this way is more understandable for the student, and more information is stored in memory. For training, virtual reality glasses, headphones, and manipulators or hands are used. Tuition costs are much lower than traditional college education. After completing the training, each student receives knowledge that will be passed on to him by the best teachers. Most importantly, the student has the opportunity to gain the experience [3,5].

Benefits of VR in education:

1. visibility of processes
2. you can show anything you want
3. involvement in learning
4. possibility of distance learning
5. interesting presentation of boring material
6. training and practicing various skills

Conclusion

1. Neural networks are the greatest achievement of human thinking in the field of modern information technology. They are a way of processing information in the same way as the human brain.

Virtual reality in education

Virtual reality (VR) is a world created by technical means, transmitted to a person through his senses: vision, hearing, touch, and others (Fig. 3). Virtual reality simulates both exposure and reactions to exposure. Virtual reality in education or virtual education is the process and result of the communicative interaction of subjects and objects in the virtual education sphere [1].

2. Artificial intelligence is a set of programs for solving various problems using neural network technologies, which provide adaptive solutions to assigned problems.

3. Virtual reality, through software and hardware, creates an artificial reality that creates great prospects in education and knowledge of the world.

4. The above technologies must be intensively developed and applied everywhere, including in Azerbaijan.

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